

TAXONOMY, ECOLOGY, AND CONSERVATION OF AGLAOMORPHA (DRYNARIA) IN COMMON HOST TREES IN OLUTANGA, ZAMBOANGA SIBUGAY

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ABSTRACT

This study was conducted to determine the taxonomy, ecology, and conservation of Aglaomorpha in common host trees in Olutanga, Zamboanga Sibugay, to develop potential conservation and management strategies, and help in the increase of awareness among people in the locality. Its primary target is to determine the species composition, richness, and relative abundance of Aglaomorpha and how common host trees affect its diversity. The study employed quadrat sampling and a non-random selective method to gather data. The descriptive taxonomic parameters were calculated using the Shannon index and Simpson index. These were quantified for each host tree using PAST software. Significant differences in the diversity indices were determined using One-way ANOVA. Findings revealed that only *Cocos nucifera* and *Mangifera indica* were common in all study areas and only two Aglaomorpha species were identified in the six barangays of Olutanga. A significant difference existed on the species composition, richness, and relative abundance of Kabkab among common host tree species. It was concluded that Olutanga is less diverse in ferns specifically Aglaomorpha species and local environmental activities like selective planting and logging greatly contributed to this. Further study is advised to directly pinpoint the cause of decreasing diversity of Aglaomorpha in Olutanga.

Keywords: *Aglaomorpha*¹, *Kabkab*², *Taxonomy*³, *Ecology*⁴, *Conservation*⁵, *Species Diversity*⁶

INTRODUCTION

Fifteen (15) species of ferns are endemic to the Philippines, and nine (9) species are new to Mindanao Island. There are also 18 threatened species. One species is critically endangered, seven (7) species are endangered, and ten (10) species are vulnerable. Polypodiaceae, consisting of 28 species, are the fern families with the most species, and they are also extensively spread throughout Mindanao (Amoroso et al., 2016). However, one species belonging to these families, *Drynaria quercifolia*, is threatened or vulnerable both locally and nationally (Lubos et al., 2015). The conservation status of fern species, especially *Drynaria quercifolia*, was determined based on the International Union for the Conservation of Nature (IUCN, 2017) and Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR-DAO 2017-11) classification (Lillo et al., 2020).

The Genus *Aglaomorpha* consists of about 21 species distributed from Africa to the Pacific, northwards to China, and Southwards to Australia. In the Philippines, four species were reported, namely *Drynaria quercifolia* (Linnaeus) J. Smith, *D. sparsisora* (Disvaux) Moore, *D. rigidula* (Swartz) Beddome, and *D. descensa* Copeland. *Drynaria descensa* Copel was endemic to the Philippines (Lillo et al., 2020). The species *Drynaria quercifolia* (Linn) Sm., *D. sparsisora* (Desv.), and Moore, *D. rigidula* (Sw.) were found in Bukidnon, Philippines (Lubos et al., 2015).

The Philippines is regarded as one of the world's megadiverse countries. The Philippines has many indigenous plant species due to its 7,107 islands and islets. However, the country is considered one of the world's biodiversity hotspots. It implies that while the country is ecologically diverse, its ecosystems are among the most vulnerable in the world. Natural and human causes have cost the country a significant number of species in recent decades (Lubos et al., 2015). Plants have an essential role in ecosystem functions such as soil fertility and stability, water availability, and pest management. These several considerations should be taken into account when making rangeland vegetation management decisions. In the field of conservation biology, biological diversity is becoming increasingly essential. Multiple studies have used changes in species richness and relative abundance caused by disruptions in continuous habitats to recommend or assess management decisions about which conservation actions are needed to ensure the species or a community of species' survival (Stephen & Sánchez, 2014).

In Southeast Asia, there are over 4400 fern species (Rahmad & Akomolafe, 2018). Based on recent classifications, the Philippines' vascular plant diversity comprises an estimated 1,100 species of ferns and lycophytes dispersed throughout 154 genera and 34 families (Amoroso et al., 2016). Epiphytes are regarded to be an essential part of the world's plant diversity. They account for 10% of all vascular plant species on the planet. These creatures are abundant in the tropical rainforest, with up to 25,000 different species of vascular epiphytes found primarily in the tropics (Nieder et al., 2001). In nature, symbiotic relationships are common. The ability to associate with various partners (i.e., broad specificity) may enable species to persist in dynamic or degraded habitats despite fluctuations in the availability of any given partner. It is crucial to understand how species

interactions differ across landscapes to predict the direct and indirect effects of environmental degradation on species conservation (Kartzinel et al., 2013).

Ferns are extremely sensitive to air humidity and temperature, making them suitable bio-indicators. Scheffers et al. (2014) also emphasized that epiphytes are also significant as a sanctuary for amphibians and reptiles in the canopy of tropical rainforests (Pouteau et al. 2016).

Many Asian countries, including China, Vietnam, Thailand, and Taiwan, cultivate and use *Drynaria* as a medicinal plant. Arunachalam & Thatheyus (2008) reported that the rhizome of *Drynaria* is used to treat typhoid fever, dyspepsia, cough, arthralgia, cephalalgia, diarrhea, nasty ulcers, and inflammation. It is a medication that is only used to treat migraines. This view is supported by Khan et al. (2007). The rhizome of *Drynaria* has been demonstrated to aid in the prevention and treatment of periodontal disease's devastating loss of gums and alveolar bone. *Drynaria* has also been found to aid in the restoration and maintenance of dental health by promoting the formation of alveolar bone and the periodontal ligament (English, 2014). Aside from its medicinal purpose, it is also used as an ornamental plant in the Philippines (Lillo et al., 2020).

The epiphyte species richness and composition varied greatly depending on the host species (Muñoz, 2003). Although people have some understanding of the significance of epiphytic ferns in forests, the knowledge of the ecology of epiphytic ferns is still quite restricted (Praptosuwiryo et al., 2019). A considerable number of lower group plant species, including pteridophytes, specifically epiphytic ferns, are threatened, primarily to indiscriminate collecting and forest destruction. As a result, preserving pteridophytes, which are significant for their medical and ornamental significance, is crucial.

Based on the reported data from the previous studies conducted in the Philippines regarding the vulnerability of Kabkab and its importance, the researcher can now focus on identifying the species composition, richness, and relative abundance of *Aglaomorpha* in common host trees of her locality, to fill out the lack of information of this certain species. With the identified common host trees and conservation status of *Aglaomorpha* in the locality, the researcher desires that the Local Government of Olotanga, Zamboanga Sibugay, and other neighboring municipalities can make use of this study as a reference for making conservation plans and efforts for this under-utilized species of epiphytic ferns.

Taxonomy, Ecology, and Conservation of *Aglaomorpha* in Common Host Trees

The common names of *Aglaomorpha* are Oakleaf fern or basket fern. Lillo et al. (2020) also noted that the common name in Cebuano is Kabkab. Chowdhury (2014) supports this view. It is also called Pakpak-lawin (Lubos et al., 2015). *Drynaria* or *Aglaomorpha* is a fern genus that can be epiphytic, which grows on trees, or epipetric, which grows on the ground or rocks. Nectar-secreting structures have been discovered near the base or underside of the frond lobes. They make nectar that's high in amino acids and carbohydrates. As a result, it plays a significant economic role in many nations,

particularly in Asia. *Drynaria* grows in pure colonies on exposed, dry tree trunks, often covering the entire trunk (Datar et al., 2010).

They do not produce sori and are tenacious, not shedding after turning brown and withering. The common name comes from their structure that they form a distinctive 'basket' that collects rubbish and organic material. The accumulated waste decomposes into humus, supplying nutrients to the plants that they would not have gotten otherwise because they were suspended above the ground. Both fronds originate from rhizomes, usually attached to a tree or a rock (Prasanna & Anuradha, 2016). Nest leaves (slender, delicate, short-lived, turn brown on senescence, shed on drying) and bracket leaves (plate-like, resembling oak leaves, strong, leathery, remain attached to creeping rhizome after senescence, decay as standing dead) are the two types of leaves produced by this fern. The bracket leaves act as funnels, collecting waste from the canopy's water run-off (Sridhar et al., 2006).

Negi et al. (2009) added that the presence of two types of fronds distinguishes *Drynaria*: fertile foliage fronds and sterile nest fronds. Hence, they are dimorphic. Fertile fronds are often much shorter than sterile fronds. The dark green fronds have extended stalks 2–4 feet (0.61–1.22 m) long. They have sori (structures that produce and contain spores) on the bottom surfaces and are strongly lobed or pinnate. The sterile fronds are persistent and dry, with a conspicuous brown rachis that is hairy, scaly, or glabrous. The lamina is simple, pinnatifid, ovate or lanceolate, deeply lobed, persistent, dry, hairy or glabrous, and usually much shorter than the fertile ones. The primary lateral veins protrude from the lower surface, forming a well-formed, nearly continuous row of areolae with or without free included veinlets. For the fertile fronds, the stipes are conspicuous, usually winged due to decurrent lamina bases, the upper surface is grooved, hairy, and the lamina is simple, pinnatifid. Still, the edge is deeply lobed almost to the rachis, and the lobes are usually decurrent on the stipe. The veins are abundantly anastomosing, although the costal areolae are not as conspicuous as in sterile fronds.

The Rhizomes are wooly and 2cm thick. *Drynaria* rhizomes are creeping and thickly coated in brown scales, measuring 20-25mm in length, 0.7-2.5mm in width, and are squishy. The base of the stipes is winged, and the lamina is not divided into individual leaflets. Sori have a circular and round shape. Spores are 37.5-55 microns length and 22.5-37.5 microns broad (Prasanna & Anuradha, 2016). Arunachalam & Thatheyus (2008) also reported that the rhizome of *Drynaria* is used to treat typhoid fever, dyspepsia, cough, arthralgia, cephalalgia, diarrhea, nasty ulcers, and inflammation. It is a medication that is only used to treat migraines. This view is supported by Khan et al. (2007).

An epiphyte is a plant that obtains moisture and nutrients from the air and rain and grows on another plant. (Merriam-Webster, n.d.). Epiphytic plants are commonly called "air plants" because they appear to hang in mid-air. They only rely on their host plants for physical support, not for nutrition. Orchids, ferns, and pineapple family members are examples of tropical epiphytes. Moreover, Nieder et al. (2001) discuss that epiphytes make up about ten percent of all vascular plant species. They are nearly entirely found in tropical forests. As a result, they account for a significant portion of world plant biodiversity

(10 percent of all species) and up to 25% of all vascular plant species in tropical countries. Epiphytes are classified into several groups based on (i) their life cycle timing (holo- and Hemi-epiphytes), (ii) their adherence to bark (facultative, obligate, and accidental epiphytes), (iii) their light requirements (sun, shade-tolerance), (iv) their preferred substrate exploitation (bole, twigs, branch), and (v) their nutritional mode.

Vascular epiphytes impact the microclimate in tropical tree crowns both within individual microsites and between tree crowns with diverse epiphyte development. They provide microsites with lower temperatures and less water loss through evapotranspiration than epiphyte-free regions inside the same tree crown on hot and cloudless days (Stuntz et al., 2002). Vascular epiphytes, including ferns, can be classified into three groups: their drought tolerance such as hygrophytes, mesophytes, and xerophytes types of plants. Hygrophytes are drought-resistant and strictly adapted to hygrophilous environments. Mesophytic epiphytes do not have any special adaptations, although they thrive in areas with plenty of water. They are commonly seen sympatrically with hygrophytes. They can create a suspended soil and are therefore known as humus-collectors, demonstrating growth patterns that allow them to store humus and entrap besides nutrients and water (Dubuisson et al., 2009). Drynarioid ferns use numerous mechanisms to gather litter: certain *Drynaria* species have specialized humus-collecting blades, while others, as well as some *Aglaomorpha* species, have fronds that are all basally expanded. Ferns that live in a mutualistic relationship with ants have a distinct method for dealing with limited nutrition access. Both highly specialized cases are known from the family of Polypodiaceae.

A host tree is a plant that assists, shelters or protects the growth of another plant, such as those used for nursing crops (Webster's Revised Unabridged Dictionary, 1913). Many plants (mainly trees) serve as hosts, providing a substrate, "a spot in the sun," and, in the case of mistletoes, water and carbohydrates. Because tree species range in various characteristics (such as bark qualities and foliage density), the growing circumstances for these structurally dependent plants may be highly reliant on the host species (Wagner, Mendieta-Leiva, & Zotz, 2015). Trees create vertical microhabitats that epiphytes take advantage of as they grow (Flores-Palacios & García-Franco, 2006). Vascular epiphytes, which are structurally dependent on their hosts, grow in a three-dimensional matrix defined by their hosts (Einzmann et al., 2015). According to Callaway et al. (2002), epiphytes grow and establish themselves on tree bark and branches and trapped soil or organic debris in fissures in the bark surface or branches. The forests' towering and well-stratified trees provide an ideal environment for epiphytic Pteridophytes to thrive. On the other hand, a few other ferns favor open tree trunks and branches. *Mangifera indica*, *Artocarpus heterophyllus*, *Careya arborea*, *Terminalia tomentosa*, and other trees host pteridophytes (Datar et al., 2010).

Epiphytes benefit significantly from the presence of their host trees, and the whole relationship is thus favorable, at least in one direction. We might expect host species to be highly redundant because the primary purpose of the host appears to be to create substrate above the forest floor. However many studies have demonstrated that epiphytes vary in number among potential host species and that many properties of host

tree species may correlate with epiphyte occurrence and abundance (Woods 2013, Vergara-Torres et al., 2010). Epiphytic ferns' diversity growing on palm trees, the host species, demonstrates that palm trees (*Arecaceae*) are essential for fern diversity (Praptosuwiryo et al., 2019). The host trees common to *Drynaria quercifolia* are *Pinus nigra*, *Samanea saman*, *Cassia fistula*, *Ficus benjamina*, *Azadiractha indica*, *Bambusa vulgaris* (Rahmad & Akomolafe, 2018), and *Arenga undulatifolia* (Praptosuwiryo et al., 2019).

Species Richness. Moore (2013) explains that species richness (S) refers to the number of species found in a given area or region. One can determine a region's species richness through sampling or a census. Because the observer defines the "region," species richness has been divided into three components to account for differences in spatial scale. The species richness that occurs within a specific area within a region smaller than the species' whole distribution is called *Alpha* diversity, also known as point diversity. The second, which is the rate at which species richness grows when one walks in a straight line across an area from one habitat to another, is known as *Beta* diversity. It also means that it is the pace at which species richness changes as a function of spatial scale. The third, the species richness of a whole region, is referred to as gamma diversity. As the area studied grows larger, alpha diversity approaches gamma diversity, while beta diversity approaches zero.

Fedor & Zvaríková (2019) supported this view that species richness measures the diversity of species based on a simple count of the number of species in a given sample. It is more effectively represented as species richness pre-unit area, with levels ranging from alpha (for a single site) to gamma (for an entire study area). Gotelli & Colwell (2011) pointed out that many community ecologists and conservation biologists consider measuring species richness a critical goal. The number of individuals collected and the number, size, and spatial arrangement of samples are susceptible to species richness counts. They assumed that one or more samples had been taken, either by collection or observation, from one or more assemblages for some defined group or groups of organisms for estimating species richness. They differentiated between two types of data utilized in richness studies: (1) incidence data, in which each species discovered in a sample from an assemblage is documented as being present, and (2) abundance data, in which each species' abundance is tallied within each sample. Naturally, one can translate abundance data to incidence data, but not the other way around.

Species richness estimates require particular statistical approaches to account for differences in sampling effort and abundance. They suggested sample-based rarefaction with unconditional variances, with modifications for the number of individuals sampled, for evaluating species richness among different groups. Using sample-based and individual-based rarefaction algorithms enables meaningful comparisons of diversity samples with similar numbers of individuals and samples. Amoroso et al. (2016) also emphasized that human activities such as converting forests to agricultural or industrial lands, and pollution, impact species richness.

The Shannon-Wiener diversity index has been widely employed in environmental research to measure ecosystem species richness and abundance (Omayio & Mzungu, 2019). It is used in ecological literature to describe a measurement that combines two factors, such as the number of species in a community or richness and the relative frequency of these species or equitability (Di Bitetti, 2000).

Species Composition. The identity of all the diverse organisms that make up a community is known as species composition (Cleland, 2011). It is crucial information when figuring out how an ecosystem functions and how different essential organisms are to the environment. Patterson, B. & Atmar, W. (2000) noted that local extinction had shaped the species composition.

Species richness and composition are the two main components of species diversity. While most studies on the relationship between ecosystem diversity and stability have focused on species richness, change in species composition provides the mechanical basis for explaining the association between species richness and ecosystem function. Because species differ in resource consumption, environmental tolerances, and interactions with other species, species composition significantly impacts ecosystem functioning and stability (Cleland 2011). Because species composition is unique to each community, ecologists looking for broad community patterns typically consider the effects of species composition as noise. It is vital to compare the effects of broad community features like species richness to the consequences of species composition to avoid oversimplification. Because island biotas are notoriously sensitive to certain introduced species, the implications of introducing species to an island may depend heavily on identifying the species rather than the number of species (Lawler, 1993).

Relative Abundance. Preston (1948) notes that relative abundance refers to the relationship between the number of individuals in one species and the number of individuals in another. Simpson's Index of Diversity (D) is used to calculate the relative abundance of species in an area. Another formula is used to calculate the relative abundance of epiphyte or vine species. The relative abundance of epiphytes 'i' is estimated as the frequency of occurrence (%FO), expressed as a percentage of all sampled trees within the subplot, irrespective of identity, where species 'i' is present (Muñoz, A., 2003).

Threats. Ferns under the understory of trees adapted to the usually shaded, sometimes damp, and usually more consistent soil moisture of the forest floor are particularly vulnerable to logging and significant forest devastation. Logging destroys large swathes of forests where epiphytes live on tree trunks and limbs. Due to global climate change, dramatic changes in precipitation patterns may result in prolonged dry periods (Anderson, O. R. 2021). The desiccation tolerances of the epiphytic ferns are exceeded. The majority of the ferns found along the roadside were damaged, destroyed, and lost due to road building, roadside clearing, and excavation for telecommunications and electrical uses. Construction operations, maintenance activities, inappropriate landscape techniques, and unplanned waste disposal contributed to the surge in damage and devastation. (Ekanayake et al., 2001).

Since *Aglaomorpha* is an epiphytic fern that requires a host tree for attachment or mechanical support, host tree identity must also be put into consideration (Callaway et al., 2002; Einzmann et al., 2015; Vergara-Torres et al., 2010; Wagner, Mendieta-Leiva & Zotz, 2015; Woods, 2013). There were studies already conducted regarding *Kabkab* in some foreign countries like India (Arunachalam, 2008; Datar, 2010; Khan et al., 2007; Korwar, 2010), Malaysia (Rahmad & Akomolafe, 2018), and other places in the Philippines like Davao Oriental (Amoroso et al., 2016) Cagayan de Oro (Lubos et al., 2015) and Cebu Island (Lillo et al., 2020). However, there were no studies conducted yet, in which these variables were involved. Hence, to address this gap, this study is proposed to focus on the species composition, richness, and relative abundance of *Aglaomorpha* (*Drynaria*) in common host trees in Olutanga, Zamboanga Sibugay.

Research Questions

The study aimed to identify the species composition, richness, and relative abundance of *Aglaomorpha* (*Drynaria*) in common host trees in Olutanga, Zamboanga Sibugay. More specifically, the study sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What are the identified common host trees of *Aglaomorpha* in the sampling areas?
 2. What is the species composition of *Aglaomorpha* in the identified common host trees?
 3. What is the species richness of *Aglaomorpha* in the identified common host trees?
 4. What is the relative abundance of *Aglaomorpha* in the identified common host trees?
 5. Is there a significant difference on species composition, richness, and relative abundance of *Aglaomorpha* among common host tree species?
 6. What local environmental activities affect the species composition, richness and relative abundance of *Aglaomorpha* in the common host trees?
 7. Based on the findings, what learning activity sheet can be developed to promote the conservation of *Aglaomorpha* from the study?
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METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used the non-experimental quantitative research design, which is descriptive comparative. Descriptive designs gather data on variables without altering the environment or modifying any variables. Therefore, they do not assess possible cause and effect. They differ from observational designs in that no comparison groups are included (Baker, 2017). No modification of an independent variable, no random assignment to groups, and often the inclusion of a control or comparison group are all known characteristics of descriptive, comparative research studies. (Cantrell, 2011). The

study employs *Alpha* Taxonomy, which is concerned with defining and naming biodiversity at the species level or lower, regardless of the instruments used by the scientist (Seifert, 2009). *Alpha*-taxonomy is from the Greek τάξις, taxis which means arrangement, and νόμος, nomos which means law (Hortolà, 2018).

Research Environment

The study was conducted in the Municipality of Olutanga, Zamboanga Sibugay in varied sampling sites of barangay Calais, Esperanza, Fama, Gandaan, Kahayagan, and Villacorte. The mean annual relative humidity in Olutanga is as high as 83% occurring in July and October. The least humid condition for the area is in the summer month of March, with an average amount of 78%. October is the wettest, with a monthly average rainfall of 178.9 mm. On the other hand, the month of February is the driest, with a mean monthly rainfall of 43.7 mm. The average annual rainfall recorded based on years of data is 1266.5 mm.

The sites ranged in elevation from 12.9 meters to 42.5 meters above sea level. Gandaan has the lowest elevation, while Fama has the highest elevation. The average high temperature at the study sites was similar, which is 31°C from January to April and 23°C for the average low temperature.

Three study sites were used in each barangay. A total of 18 study sites were utilized for the entire study area. Each barangay has sites with direct and indirect sunlight.

Figure 2. *Satellite map of the study area* (Source: <https://bit.ly/3AuXTdt>)

Study Area

The geographical coordinates of all study sites of the study area are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Geographical Coordinates of Study Sites in Olutanga, Zamboanga Sibugay.

STUDY SITES	LATITUDE (N)	LONGITUDE (E)
CALAIS		
1 km from Calais fish port to Calais road	7°22'52.27"	122°48'46.2"
1 km from site 1 to Laparay road	7°23'63"	122°49'6.59"
Approximately 926 m from site 2 to San Jose boundary	7°22'33.6"	122°49'27.3"
ESPERANZA		
Approximately 760 m From San Isidro Labrador Chapel to San Jose bridge	7°22'11.06"	122°49'6.61"
1 km from chapel to Sta. Maria road	7°21'12.33"	122°49'18"
1 km from Chapel to Noque road	7°21'43.35"	122°49'47.6"
FAMA		
Approximately 884 m from the boundary of Noque to Fama covered court	7°21'35.21"	122°50'46.5"
From covered court to Villacorte boundary	7°20'43.89"	122°50'58.6"
Approximately 600 m of Fama-Aurora road	7°20'12.7"	122°51'14.4"
GANDAAN		
Approximately 789 m from Gandaan fish port to Gandaan-Sta Maria road	7°19'41.35"	122°48'58.7"
Approximately 637 m from school to San Isidro boundary	7°19'27.31"	122°49'11"
Approximately 804 m of Gandaan-Sta Maria road	7°20'5.86"	122°49'10.4"

KAHAYAGAN

Approximately 1 km from the boundary of Noque to Municipal Solid waste management area	7°21'8.26"	122°50'24.6"
Approximately 900 m from site 1 to Kahayagan Elementary School	7°20'46.8"	122°50'31.4"
From School to Sta. Maria Road boundary	7°20'16.88"	122°50'17.6"

VILLACORTE

Approximately 664 m from the boundary of Fama to Villacorte Elementary School	7°20'11"	122°50'44"
Approximately 1.20 km from Villacorte Elementary School to the boundary of Solar	7°19'19"	122°50'35"
Approximately 975 m from Villacorte road to Nuestra Señora del Rosario Chapel	7°19'25"	122°50'03"

Table 1 shows the geographical coordinates of the three (3) study sites in each barangay of Olutanga, Zamboanga Sibugay namely Calais, Esperanza, Fama, Gandaan, Kahayagan, and Villacorte.

Sampling Technique

Quadrat sampling was employed in this study. It is a particular sort of visual inspection in which sample regions are demarcated in surveys to maximize the collection of underground species (Bichuette et al. 2015). Ten 10 x 10 m² plots were demarcated in each site. A minimum distance of 25m separated each sampling plot. A Non-random selective method was adopted where plots are preferentially located to ensure that at least one individual Kabkab species is present in each plot. A total of 180 plots were used for the entire study area. The sampling plots were identified in the field using Fields Area Measurement Mobile Application.

Data Gathering Procedure

The common host trees with attached Kabkab were counted, identified, and recorded in all sampling quadrats. To identify the different species of Drynaria, the study of Lubos, L. C., & Amoroso, V. B. (2013), which is "The identity and morphology of the three species of Drynaria (Polypodiaceae) in Bukidnon, Philippines," was used as a field guide. The researcher also consulted the Community Environment and Natural

Resources Office (CENRO) in Imelda, Zamboanga Sibugay, for the identification of some host trees.

Because most individual fern species arise from a common inseparable rhizome and form clumps, each Kabkab stipe, the whole frond originating from the rhizome, was counted as an individual fern (Rahmad & Akomolafe, 2018). The total number of Kabkab within the sampling plot per site was tallied and recorded on a notebook.

Data Analytic Technique

To analyze the data gathered, the analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to test the hypothesis if there is a significant difference (Baker, 2017) among species composition, richness, and relative abundance of aglaomorpha with host tree species. The descriptive taxonomic parameters such as species composition, richness, and relative abundance of aglaomorpha were calculated using the Shannon index and Simpson index. These were quantified for each host tree using PAST software. Significant differences in the diversity indices were determined using One-way ANOVA in PAST software (Rahmad & Akomolafe, 2018). The null hypothesis that numerous univariate data sets (in columns) have the same mean was tested using one-way ANOVA (analysis of variance), which required two or more columns of measured or counted data (Hammer et al. 2001).

Scope and Limitations of the Study

This research was focused on epiphytic fern belonging to the family Polypodiaceae, specifically the genus *Aglaomorpha* or locally known as Kabkab, in common host trees in the six select barangays in the municipality of Olutanga, Zamboanga Sibugay, namely Calais, Esperanza, Fama, Gandaan, Kahayagan, and Villacorte. Its species composition, richness, and relative abundance were measured to identify the conservation status of the said plant in the community.

Subject Matter. This study was focused on epiphytic fern belonging to the family Polypodiaceae, specifically *Aglaomorpha* or locally known as Kabkab, in common host trees.

Research Environment and Timeline. This study was conducted in various sampling sites of the barangays Calais, Esperanza, Fama, Gandaan, Kahayagan, and Villacorte in Olutanga, Zamboanga Sibugay in 2021-2022 within four months from October 2021 to January 2022.

Research Design. The study is quantitative and utilized a descriptive comparative research design in its aim at measuring the species composition, richness, and relative abundance of *Aglaomorpha* in common host trees using scientific inquiry.

Data Gathering Procedure. The common host trees with attached *Aglaomorpha* were counted, identified, and recorded in all sampling areas.

Data Analytic Technique. The analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to test the hypothesis if there is a significant difference (Baker, 2017) on species composition, richness, and relative abundance of Kabkab among host tree species. Significant differences in the diversity indices were determined using One-way ANOVA in PAST software (Rahmad & Akomolafe, 2018).

RESULTS

Common Host Trees of Aglaomorpha (Kabkab)

The presence of host trees in the study areas is presented in Table 2.

Table 2

Distribution of Observed Host trees in the Study Area

Identified host trees	Study sites					
	Calais	Esperanz a	Fama	Gandaan	Kahayaga n	Villacorte
1. <i>Acacia confusa</i>	√	X	X	X	X	X
2. <i>Annona muricata</i>	X	X	X	X	X	√
3. <i>Artocarpus heterophyllus</i>	X	√	√	√	X	X
4. <i>Chrysophyllum cainito</i>	X	√	√	X	√	√
5. <i>Citrus maxima</i>	√	X	X	X	X	X
6. <i>Cocos nucifera</i>	√	√	√	√	√	√
7. <i>Corypha elata</i>	X	X	√	X	X	√
8. <i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>	X	X	X	√	X	X
9. <i>Mangifera indica</i>	√	√	√	√	√	√

10. <i>Octomeles sumatrana</i>	X	X	X	X	X	√
11. <i>Peltophorum pterocarpum</i>	X	X	X	√	X	X
12. <i>Swietenia macrophyllaga</i>	X	X	X	X	√	X
13. <i>Terminalia catappa</i>	√	X	√	X	X	X

KEY √ means present; X means absent

Species Composition of Aglaomorpha

The identity of all the diverse organisms that make up a community is known as species composition (Cleland, 2011). The species composition of Kabkab in the identified host trees is provided in Table 3.

Table 3

Hosts of Aglaomorpha in the Study Area.

Host tree	Aglaomorpha hosted
CALAIS	
1. <i>Acacia confuse</i>	<i>Aglaomorpha quercifolia</i>
2. <i>Citrus maxima</i>	<i>Aglaomorpha quercifolia</i>
3. <i>Cocos nucifera</i>	<i>Aglaomorpha quercifolia</i>
4. <i>Mangifera indica</i>	<i>Aglaomorpha quercifolia</i>
5. <i>Terminalia catappa</i>	<i>Aglaomorpha quercifolia</i>
ESPERANZA	
1. <i>Artocarpus heterophyllus</i>	<i>Aglaomorpha quercifolia</i>
2. <i>Chrysophyllum cainito</i>	<i>Aglaomorpha quercifolia</i>
3. <i>Cocos nucifera</i>	<i>Aglaomorpha quercifolia</i>

4. *Mangifera indica* *Aglaomorpha quercifolia*

FAMA

1. *Artocarpus heterophyllus* *Aglaomorpha quercifolia*

2. *Chrysophyllum cainito* *Aglaomorpha quercifolia*

3. *Cocos nucifera* *Aglaomorpha quercifolia*

4. *Corypha elata* *Aglaomorpha quercifolia*

5. *Mangifera indica* *Aglaomorpha quercifolia*

6. *Terminalia catappa* *Aglaomorpha quercifolia*

GANDAAN

1. *Artocarpus heterophyllus* *Aglaomorpha quercifolia*

2. *Cocos nucifera* *Aglaomorpha quercifolia*

Aglaomorpha sparsisora

3. *Leucaena leucocephala* *Aglaomorpha quercifolia*

4. *Mangifera indica* *Aglaomorpha quercifolia*

5. *Peltophorum pterocarpum* *Aglaomorpha quercifolia*

KAHAYAGAN

1. *Chrysophyllum cainito* *Aglaomorpha quercifolia*

2. *Cocos nucifera* *Aglaomorpha quercifolia*

Aglaomorpha sparsisora

3. *Mangifera indica* *Aglaomorpha quercifolia*

Aglaomorpha sparsisora

4. *Swietenia macrophyllaga* *Aglaomorpha sparsisora*

VILLACORTE

1. *Annona muricata* *Aglaomorpha quercifolia*

2.	<i>Chrysophyllum cainito</i>	<i>Aglaomorpha quercifolia</i>
3.	<i>Cocos nucifera</i>	<i>Aglaomorpha quercifolia</i>
4.	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	<i>Aglaomorpha quercifolia</i>
5.	<i>Octomeles sumatrana</i>	<i>Aglaomorpha quercifolia</i>

Species Richness

Species richness measures the diversity of species based on a simple count of the number of species in a given sample (Fedor & Zvaríková, 2019). Table 4 depicts the species richness of Kabkab in host trees of the study area.

Table 4
Species Richness of Sampled Aglaomorpha in Host Trees of the Study Area

Host trees	Observed species richness
1. <i>Acacia confusa</i>	1
2. <i>Annona muricata</i>	1
3. <i>Artocarpus heterophyllus</i>	1
4. <i>Chrysophyllum cainito</i>	1
5. <i>Citrus maxima</i>	1
6. <i>Cocos nucifera</i>	2
7. <i>Corypha elata</i>	1
8. <i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>	1
9. <i>Mangifera indica</i>	2
10. <i>Octomeles sumatrana</i>	1
11. <i>Peltophorum pterocarpum</i>	1
12. <i>Swietenia macrophyllaga</i>	1
13. <i>Terminalia catappa</i>	1

Biodiversity indices

The aglaomorpha diversity indices, such as Shannon and Simpson indices, were quantified for each host tree using PAST software, depicted in Table 5.

Table 5
Diversity Indices of Sampled Aglaomorpha in Host Trees in the Study Area.

Host trees	Number of individuals	Biodiversity indices	
		Simpson Index	Shannon Index
1. <i>Acacia confusa</i>	481	0	0
2. <i>Annona muricata</i>	8	0	0
3. <i>Artocarpus heterophyllus</i>	53	0.4746	0.758
4. <i>Chrysophyllum cainito</i>	383	0.6654	1.179
5. <i>Citrus maxima</i>	10	0	0
6. <i>Cocos nucifera</i>	1003	0.7896	1.661
7. <i>Corypha elata</i>	24	0.4965	0.6897
8. <i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>	22	0	0
9. <i>Mangifera indica</i>	1285	0.7476	1.54
10. <i>Octomeles sumatrana</i>	38	0	0
11. <i>Peltophorum pterocarpum</i>	6	0	0
12. <i>Swietenia macrophyllaga</i>	9	0	0
13. <i>Terminalia catappa</i>	23	0.4537	0.6461

The hypothesis of the study is that there is no significant difference on species composition, richness, and relative abundance of Aglaomorpha among host tree species. It was tested using a 0.05 level of significance in One-way ANOVA in PAST software. The ANOVA result for species composition and richness of Aglaomorpha in host trees is provided in table 6.

Table 6

ANOVA Result for Species Composition and Richness of Aglaomorpha in Host Trees

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	426496	1	426496	4.694	0.04042
Within Groups	2.18071E06	24	90863.1		
Total	2.60721E06	25			

The ANOVA result for species relative abundance of Aglaomorpha among host trees is provided in table 7.

Table 7

ANOVA Result for Species Relative Abundance of Aglaomorpha in Host Trees

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	429414	1	429414	4.726	0.0398
Within Groups	2.18071E06	24	90863.1		
Total	2.61013E06	25			

DISCUSSION

As shown in Table 2, thirteen (13) host trees were identified in all sampling areas. One of the host trees recorded was *Octomeles sumatrana*, locally known as "binuang," located in barangay Villacorte near the national road. It is considered the island's famous landmark and known to be the largest and oldest tree in Olutanga. However, among the identified host trees, only *Cocos nucifera* and *Mangifera indica* were present or common in all study areas. This implies that these host trees are the most abundant in Olutanga. Based on an informal interview with a farmer in Esperanza, coconuts were planted purposively for copra production, which is one of the people's sources of income in the island. Other host trees also became rare due to the devastation caused by typhoons like the *Corypha elata* or "buli" in barangay Esperanza, Fama, and Kahayagan. Aside from that, people are also unaware of the ecological significance of kabkab, which is why they failed to protect the species. On the other hand, all recorded host trees were also observed to have rough bark texture. These findings are similar to the study of

Praptosuwiryo et al., 2019. Rough bark texture of the host tree is ideal for the attachment and growth of this epiphytic fern.

As provided in Table 3, a total of two (2) Kabkab species, namely *Aglaomorpha quercifolia* and *Aglaomorpha sparsisora* were recorded in all the identified host trees in the six (6) barangays of Olutanga, Zamboanga Sibugay. These epiphytic ferns could be described as not host-specific as they were found growing on more than one type of host tree (Rahmad & Akomolafe, 2018). *Aglaomorpha quercifolia* was observed in all host trees of the sampled areas. In contrast, *Aglaomorpha sparsisora* were only observed in some host trees like *Cocos nucifera* in Gandaan and Kahayagan, *Mangifera indica* in Kahayagan, and *Swietenia macrophyllaga* in Kahayagan with a correspondingly low number of individuals. This result contradicted the study of Lubos, L. C., & Amoroso, V. B. (2013). The species composition of kabkab was greatly affected by the failure of the people in protecting the species. Based on an informal interview from the barangay captain of Villacorte, they thought that kabkab would harm or make the trees thin. That is why kabkab were purposively removed. Epiphytes only rely on their host plants for physical support, not for nutrition (Merriam-Webster, n.d.).

As presented in Table 4, the highest total species richness (2 species) was recorded in *Cocos nucifera* and *Mangifera indica*. The rest of the host trees were recorded to have one species of Kabkab only. This could imply that the identity of the host tree affects the species richness of the host. This is similar to the study of Cardelus (2002) that certain host tree species have a higher diversity and number of epiphytes than others. Aside from that, *Cocos nucifera* and *Mangifera indica* were the only remaining common host trees in all sampled areas because selective planting, logging, and natural calamities greatly affected the species richness of kabkab. The majority of the ferns and host trees found along the roadside were damaged, destroyed, and lost as a result of road building, roadside clearing, and excavation for telecommunications and electrical uses based on an informal interview from the settlers. This agrees with Anderson, 2021.

Species Relative Abundance

The relative abundance of aglaomorpha was calculated in each sampling plot using the formula $\%FO_i = \left(\frac{N_i}{N}\right) \times 100$, where N_i is the number of trees on which kabkab species are recorded, and N is the total number of trees sampled within the subplots (Muñoz, 2003). *Aglaomorpha* species was most abundant in *Mangifera indica* (61%), followed by *Cocos nucifera* (46%), *Chrysophyllum cainito* (44%), and *Artocarpus heterophyllus* (27%). The hosts with the most abundant *aglaomorpha* species, namely *Mangifera indica* and *Cocos nucifera*, were also the identified common host trees. It is evident from this study that the presence and identity of the host tree in each sampling area affect the relative abundance of Kabkab. *Mangifera indica* and *Cocos nucifera* had the most abundant epiphytes. They were also the most abundant trees due to selective planting, logging, road constructions, and natural calamities. Their physical properties, also like rough bark texture, are favorable for the attachment of kabkab. Like gemelina and doldol or cotton tree, other trees on the island were not hosts to kabkab due to their

bark surface. Aside from that, Aglaomorpha grows on exposed tree trunks (Datar et. al., 2010). It agrees with Woods 2013, and Vergara-Torres et al., 2010 which demonstrated that epiphytes vary in number among potential host species and that many properties of host tree species may correlate with epiphyte occurrence and abundance. Epiphytes benefit significantly from the presence of their host tree.

A community with a Shannon index of greater than 2 is thought to be more diversified. Because the Shannon index values of all the studied host trees are less than 2, it can be concluded that they are all less diverse in fern species (Rahmad & Akomolafe, 2018). Simpson's Index of Diversity (D) is used to calculate the relative abundance of species in an area (Preston, 1948). The Simpson index of *Cocos nucifera* and *Mangifera indica* are significantly higher than the rest of the host trees (Table 5). Since *Cocos nucifera* and *Mangifera indica* were the most cultivated host trees, they were also found in each site. Their favorable characteristics as hosts contributed to the presence of kabkab epiphytes, and the common species of kabkab were found in each site. This agrees with the study of Rahmad & Akomolafe, 2018.

Based on table 6, a *p* value (Sig.) of 0.04042 was obtained. This number is lesser than the study's *alpha* level of 0.05. Therefore, there is a significant difference on the species composition and richness of aglaomorpha among host tree species. The null hypothesis was rejected. It implied that the identity of host tree species affected greatly to the diversity of Aglaomorpha in terms of species composition and richness. Because tree species range in various characteristics (such as bark qualities and foliage density), the growing circumstances for Aglaomorpha as structurally dependent plants may be highly reliant on the host species (Wagner 2015).

A *p* value (Sig.) of 0.0398 was obtained based on the result. This number is lesser than the study's *alpha* level of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. Statistically significant difference on relative abundance of Aglaomorpha among host tree species was found. In other words, species relative abundance of Aglaomorpha was dependent on the identity of host trees. Vascular epiphytes, which are structurally dependent on their hosts, grow in a three-dimensional matrix defined by their hosts (Einzmann et al., 2015).

Conclusions

The following is the summary of findings on the species composition, richness, and relative abundance of Aglaomorpha (Kabkab) in common host trees in Olutanga, Zamboanga Sibugay.

1. What are the identified common host trees of Aglaomorpha in the sampling areas?

The identified common host trees of Aglaomorpha are *Acacia confusa*, *Annona muricata*, *Artocarpus heterophyllus*, *Chrysophyllum caimito*, *Citrus maxima*, *Cocos nucifera*, *Corypha elata*, *Leucaena leucocephala*, *Mangifera indica*, *Octomeles*

sumatrana, *Peltophorum pterocarpum*, *Swietenia macrophyllaga*, and *Terminalia catappa*, but only *Cocos nucifera*, and *Mangifera indica* were present in all study areas.

2. What is the species composition of *Aglaomorpha* in the identified common host trees?

The species composition of *Aglaomorpha* in the identified common host trees is two (2) *Aglaomorpha* species namely *Aglaomorpha quercifolia* and *Aglaomorpha sparsisora* which were recorded in the six (6) barangays of Olutanga, Zamboanga Sibugay. These epiphytic ferns could be described as not host-specific as they were found growing on more than one type of host tree.

3. What is the species richness of *Aglaomorpha* in the identified common host trees?

The species richness of *Aglaomorpha* in the identified common host trees is two (2) species which was recorded in *Cocos nucifera* and *Mangifera indica*. The rest of the host trees were recorded to have one (1) species of Kabkab only. Certain host tree species have a higher diversity and number of epiphytes than others.

4. What is the relative abundance of *Aglaomorpha* in the identified common host trees?

The relative abundance of *Aglaomorpha* in the identified common host trees based on the Simpson index of diversity is 79% for *Cocos nucifera* while 75% is for *Mangifera indica*. The result is significantly higher than the rest of the host trees because the common species of *Aglaomorpha* were found in each plot. *Aglaomorpha* species were also most abundant in host trees located in indirect sunlight areas.

5. Is there a significant difference on species composition, richness, and relative abundance of *Aglaomorpha* among common host tree species?

A significant difference existed on the species composition, richness, and relative abundance of Kabkab among common host tree species using One-way ANOVA in PAST software.

6. What local environmental activities affect the species composition, richness, and relative abundance of *Aglaomorpha* in the common host trees?

Local environmental activities like selective planting of coconuts for copra production, logging, and natural calamities greatly affected the species richness of *Aglaomorpha*. Most of the ferns and host trees found along the roadside were damaged, destroyed, and lost as a result of road building, roadside clearing, and excavation for telecommunications and electrical uses based on an informal interview from the settlers.

7. Based on the findings, what learning activity sheet can be developed to promote the conservation of *Aglaomorpha* from the study?

The developed learning activity sheets are aimed to promote the conservation of *Aglaomorpha* and is based on the DepEd's Most Essential Learning Competency (MELC) in Grade 8 which is Classify organisms using the hierarchical taxonomic system (S8LT-IVh-20). (See Appendix B on page 27)

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that the six barangays of Olutanga, Zamboanga Sibugay are less diverse in terms of *Aglaomorpha* species. This could be that people are still unaware of the benefits of *Aglaomorpha*, which is why they

failed to protect the species. The majority of the ferns as well as host trees found along the roadside were damaged, destroyed, and lost as a result of road building, roadside clearing, and excavation for telecommunications and electrical uses based on an informal interview from the settlers. Because the species composition, richness and relative abundance of Aglaomorpha were influenced by *Cocos nucifera* and *Mangifera indica*, it is important to preserve these host trees. Since Aglaomorpha species are essential members of the tropical epiphytic flora, it is critical that they be better studied and conserved. The diversity of Aglaomorpha growing on *Cocos nucifera* and *Mangifera indica* clearly demonstrates that the existence of these host trees is one of the most important factors in epiphytic fern diversity. An environmental information drive regarding the ecological and conservation status of Aglaomorpha may be developed by the local government to educate the people in the locality.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following are recommended:

1. Students would understand the ecological functions of Aglaomorpha and create awareness in protecting the species.
2. The local government may develop an environmental information drive regarding the ecological and conservation status of Aglaomorpha to protect the species of Aglaomorpha and its common host trees.
3. Future researchers who will be conducting related studies are encouraged to use the result of this research as a supplement to their existing knowledge and are recommended to include a wider range of study areas for more significant results.
4. Copies of this study may be shared with the Science teachers to encourage them to conduct studies on other local organisms to protect the natural resources in the locality, especially the vulnerable species.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher's ability to conduct the research study was supported by ethical considerations. It provided a comprehensive overview of the study process, which may aid in avoiding unwanted scenarios that could result in unfavorable outcomes. As a result, ethical considerations enhanced the development strategy plan for the duration of the research. The ethical considerations that were observed in the study are the following:

Informed Consent and Informed Assent. A written and signed consent form which certifies that the LGU of Olutanga, as well as each barangay captain, willingly agrees to use the barangay as the study site, and a consent letter from the Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR) were prepared before the data gathering.

Scientific Validity. The scientific method was observed to maintain the highest level of objectivity in discussions and analyses throughout the research.

Favorable Risk-Benefit Ratio. It was assured that minimum or no single species was harmed nor exploited during the study. In both the short and long term, the study's

potential benefits were assessed, confirmed, and stated. The requirement to examine the scientific quality of the experiments and if the experiments will have important scientific benefits is also part of the responsibilities.

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